

Hand-out CESSDA SAW webinar 2:

Research Data Management, 23rd June 2016

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This document supports webinar 2 on Research Data Management, which was created in the CESSDA SaW project. The webinar targeted future trainers, who can use this document as a reference list, when preparing trainings on RDM for different target audiences. Major topics are covered here.

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1 CESSDA

[CESSDA – Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives](#)

[CESSDA SaW – Strengthening and Widening CESSDA](#)

[The ESFRI Roadmap 2016](#)

[ADP – Slovenian Social Science Data Archives](#)

2 Definitions of Research Data Management

[Planning for Sharing \(UKDA\)](#)

[Why Are Research Data Managed and Reused? \(FSD\)](#)

[Research Data Life-Cycle \(CESSDA\)](#)

[Research Data Life-Cycle \(UKDA\)](#)

3 Benefits and Advantages of RDM

[Data Management Plans Learning Objectives \(MANTRA\)](#)

[Data management planning \(UKDA\)](#)

[Research Data Management \(CESSDA\)](#)

[Data management planning \(UKDS\)](#)

4 Definition of Data Management Planning

[Data management plan \(MANTRA\)](#)

[Data Management Planning \(FSD\)](#)

[Research Data Management Plans \(CESSDA\)](#)

5 Structure and Components of DMP

[Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020, February 2016 \(H2020\)](#)

[Data Management Planning \(FSD\)](#)

[Data Management Planning \(CESSDA\)](#)

[Data management planning for ESRC researchers \(UKDS\)](#)

6 Data management plan checklist

[Data management checklist \(UKDS\)](#)

[Checklist for a Data Management Plan \(DCC\)](#)

[DANS DMP template \(DANS\)](#)

[Briefing Paper Research Data Management \(OpenAIRE\)](#)

7 DM & DMP Tools

[About DMPonline and how to customise it for your institution \(DCC\)](#)

[Resources and templates \(IASSIST\)](#)

[Public DMPS \(DMPTool\)](#)

8 Stakeholders

[Roles & Responsibilities \(UKDA\)](#)

[Preparing research data for open access, Guide for data producers \(ADP\)](#)

9 Examples from ADP

[ADP workshop for librarians \(videolectures\), Ljubljana 2014](#)

[ADP seminar for researchers \(videolectures\), Ljubljana 2014](#)

[ADP course for doctoral students \(videolectures\), Ljubljana 2015](#)